

Evaluation

Table 1. Summary of the size, contiguity, correctness, and completeness statistics for CHM13 Shasta assembly. We evaluated the assembly with [QUAST 5.1.0rcr1](#) (Gurevich *et al.*, 2013) using [T2T-CHM13 v1.1](#) as the reference (Nurk *et al.*, 2022).

SIZE	CONTIGUITY			CORRECTNESS		COMPLETENESS
Assembly size (Gb)	N50 (Mb)	NG50 (Mb)	NGA50 (Mb)	mismatches per 100 kbp	indels per 100 kbp	Genome fraction
2.96	91.98	91.98	87.79	16	42	96.84

Table 2. Assembly gene completeness metrics from a asmgene reference-based analysis (Li, 2018) using Ensembl transcripts mapped to the [T2T-CHM13 v1.1](#) reference and the Shasta 0.9.0 assembly. This analysis is similar to BUSCO, but uses all the genes in the human genome.

Metric	Description	genesToReference	geneToAssembly	Percent
full_sgl	Complete single-copy genes	34582	34480	99.71%
full_dup	Misassembled as multi-copy genes	0	4	0.01%
frag	Fragmented genes	0	4	0.01%
part50+	Genes mapped over 50% of their length	0	28	0.08%
part10+	Genes mapped over 10% of their length	0	2	0.01%
part10-	Genes mapped below 10% of their length or unmapped	0	64	0.19%
dup_cnt	Fraction of missing multi-copy genes	1172	1101	6.06%

Figure 1. NGx plot showing contig lengths and their cumulative length in order of descending contig size for CHM13 reads assembled with Shasta 0.9.0 (blue line), CHM13 reads assembled with Shasta 0.1.0 (green; Shafin *et al.*, 2020) and the chromosome arm lengths of the T2T-CHM13 v1.1 assembly (purple). The Shasta 0.9.0 assembly has three contigs that span nearly the length of whole chromosomes. Plotted using a custom script available at https://github.com/rorigro/GFAse/blob/main/scripts/plot_ngx.py.

Figure 2. Single-stranded GFA of CHM13 rel8 ONT reads assembled with Shasta 0.9.0. Contigs are colored and labeled according to their corresponding human chromosome number and arm (p=short,q=long). Plotted using Bandage (Wick *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 3. Assembled contigs are plotted in blue and orange above chromosome ideograms of CHM13 T2Tv1.1 reference. Three chromosomes were assembled in essentially one contig (chr8, chr11, chrX), minus the telomeres, and with small gaps in centromeric higher-order repeats (HORs). Thirty chromosome arms are reconstructed in one contig, minus telomeres. However, gaps in the assembly remain in difficult to assembly regions. For example, the acrocentric arms of chr13 and chr15; pericentromeric regions in chr1, chr9 and chr16; and the centromeres of chr17, chr18, chr19, and chr22. The ideogram was plotted in R using the script: <https://github.com/mrvollger/asm-to-reference-alignment/blob/main/workflow/scripts/ideogram.R>

References

- Gurevich,A. *et al.* (2013) QUILT: quality assessment tool for genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics*, **29**, 1072–1075.
- Li,H. (2018) Minimap2: pairwise alignment for nucleotide sequences. *Bioinformatics*, **34**, 3094–3100.
- Nurk,S. *et al.* (2022) The complete sequence of a human genome. *Science*, **376**, 44–53.
- Shafin,K. *et al.* (2020) Nanopore sequencing and the Shasta toolkit enable efficient de novo assembly of eleven human genomes. *Nat. Biotechnol.*, **38**, 1044–1053.
- Wick,R.R. *et al.* (2015) Bandage: interactive visualization of de novo genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics*, **31**, 3350–3352.